

Optimisation Of Software Component Selection: Heuristic Methods For Improving The Selection Of Components In Libraries

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Abstract

Selecting high-quality software components to build computer applications that simultaneously meet user needs represents a major challenge. Mathematical models and optimization tools exist in the literature to facilitate the selection of components for experimentation and to aid decision-making in complex selection processes. However, these exact methods can only identify a single optimal solution within a limited set, due to the difficulties in managing the memory of the solvers associated with these tools and the computational time required for the solutions. In this paper, we propose a heuristic approach based on genetic methods. These models and genetic algorithms allow the classification of selected components according to multiple objectives based on functional coverage, licensing, and component learning time. Our approach enables us to address component selection involving often conflicting objectives. The methodology used considers software components from various markets (ComponentSource, WordPress) and employs non-dominated sorting genetic algorithms to distribute solutions across a so-called Pareto front. Our models will help find a good compromise between different, often conflicting objectives, including decision-maker preferences, budgetary constraints, and project deadlines.

Keywords— Software component selection, multi-objective optimization, Pareto front, genetic algorithm, non-dominated sorting

I. INTRODUCTION

The information processed by software development companies has become increasingly varied and complex in recent decades. It comes mainly from multiple data sources with growing volumes of information. This complexity impacts the development time of software applications, the time it takes to bring these software products to market, and development costs. As a result, a new approach to building applications has emerged, using reusable software components. This approach offers many advantages. These include: reduced development time, resulting in shorter time-to-market for software products; reduced complexity in the development of these software applications; and improved quality of the software products developed. In fact, the to building software applications is based on the use of software components that have already been developed and tested, on the one hand, and on the other hand, on improving the selling price of these products on the component markets.

This new technique for assembling software components therefore takes into account the construction of high-quality, reliable applications. When developing high-quality applications, selecting components from these software component markets is a major concern for software developers. Consequently, two main methods for solving the problem of optimal component selection are proposed. These are exact methods and heuristic methods applied to the selection of software components in component markets. Exact methods are based on mathematical models, algorithms and optimisation tools [1]. These are methods that allow optimal solutions

to be found in a set of k small components and in a very limited search time [2]. These optimisation tools are software programs with solvers that allow the models developed to be tested and assist in decision-making for complex selection problems. However, they are not suitable for selecting a large number of k candidate components due to the difficulties in managing the memory of their solvers and also the calculation time required for selection from a large set of components [3]. We note that nowadays, component selection processes are becoming difficult, NP-complex problems. Therefore, to solve the software component selection problems outlined above, we propose a second approach. This approach concerns the approximate method of software component selection, also known as the heuristic approach with artificial intelligence algorithms. This approach is based on a combination of a mathematical optimisation model in [3] and genetic algorithms. It will enable us to solve NP-hard problems such as ours on the one hand, and on the other hand to find solutions that strike a good balance between the quality of the selected components and the computation time of the solvers used to obtain the best results. This paper deals with the selection of software components from various software markets based on quality characteristics, financial cost and adaptation effort using a hybrid optimisation method that takes into account a combination of mathematical optimisation models and genetic algorithms. The aim is to develop a software environment to:

- Improve the software component selection process
- Establish a compromise between the quality of software components to be selected and the computing time required for their selection.
- Propose a strategy based on component search and selection algorithms to improve the component selection process for various software component markets.
- Propose an approximate method for solving software component selection based on artificial intelligence methods for classifying software components according to the type of software to be built.

The rest of this paper is organised as follows. The first section presents the introduction. The second section concerns the state of the art. The third section deals with the models and selection methods developed. The fourth section concerns the validation of the models. In the fifth section, we present the conclusion and outlook.

II. THE STATE OF THE ART

The problems involved in selecting reusable software components are difficult combinatorial optimisation problems that are NP-hard to solve, given the diversity of component markets and the variety of versions of these components that accumulate on sites. Several research projects related to combinatorial optimisation problems have been applied in the fields of telecommunications, maintenance operations and public services [4]. With regard to the selection of software components, work is being carried out on the use of optimisation tools and models [5] [6] [7]. Thus, in [3] [5], the authors developed optimisation models based on integer linear programming with constraints. These optimisation models were validated using the solvers in the Cplex Studio 12.2 and Cplex Studio IDE 12.8.0 optimisation tools. The authors aim to show that the quality of the selected components takes into account several important indicators such as quality characteristics, financial cost and adaptation effort. Indeed, the authors of [3] have shown that adaptation effort is a very important factor that impacts the quality of components selected from a set of available components that are candidates for selection for the construction of a high-quality, reliable modular application. Multi-objective and multi-period optimisation models have also been developed to improve incrementally developed software systems [7] [8]. Thus, a mathematical optimisation model has been constructed to select and integrate different alternatives with the aim of improving the performance and reliability of the software system [7]. In [8], the authors proposed a multi-

objective optimisation model for selecting the best components from a set of various software components such as off-the-shelf components, internally developed components, or free and reusable components. In [9], the authors developed a multi-objective model to examine the levels of importance of the criteria for free software components considered for the development of e-commerce websites.

These optimisation models are based on mathematical programming models with constraints, which are solved using optimisation tool solvers. This method of exact solution of NP-completeness problems poses difficulties related to the size of the set of software components eligible for selection on the one hand, and on the other hand, to the exponential and very memory-intensive consumption of our computers. The exact resolution method used poses a memory management problem when selecting from a large set. Thus, to solve the problems identified above, research has focused on the areas of resolution using heuristic approaches known as approximate methods [10]. These methods make it possible to arrive at acceptable solutions to the complex problems posed. Within this framework of resolution using heuristic approaches, several research projects have been conducted in various fields such as transport, urban planning, biology and computer science [11] [12]. In the field of biology, for example, authors have used heuristic methods, which form the basis of artificial intelligence, to understand animal behaviour. In [11], the particle swarm optimisation algorithm is used as a heuristic approach for the optimal selection of web services. Their work is based on the selection of web services linked to the quality of service of these software components.

III. RELATED WORK

A. Mathematical Optimisation Model Developed

We have developed an optimisation model based on component quality criteria such as characteristics, financial cost and the effort required to adapt the software component. This model compensates for the lack of models that take adaptation effort into account in the literature [1] [13] [14]. We have thus defined a function that takes its values from a set of 3-tuples of real numbers designating the characteristics of the software components. It is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{R}^n &\longrightarrow \mathbb{R} \\ (x_i, C_i, t_i)_{i \in \mathbb{N}} &\longmapsto f_i(x_i, C_i, t_i)_{i \in \mathbb{N}} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where

- x_i denotes whether or not a component can be chosen and takes its values from the set $\{0,1\}$,
- C_i denotes the price of component i . It is represented by the normalised cost of the component.
- t_i denotes the standardised adaptation time for any component i .

The solutions to the functions f_i are actual scores used, on the one hand, to optimise the selection of software components from the set S_c of available components and, on the other hand, to balance the relationship between financial cost and adaptation time using the adaptation coefficient α . This coefficient establishes the connection between parameters such as financial cost and component maintenance time.

Equation (1) was used to obtain the following linear optimisation model under constraints :

$$f_i(x_i, C_i, T_i)_{i \in \mathbb{N}} = kx_i + [\alpha C_i + (1 - \alpha)T_i]x_i \text{ avec } k \in \mathbb{R} \quad (2)$$

with

- $k = \sum_{h \in A} W_h q_{hi}$
- W_h = weight assigned to quality attribute $h \in A$;
- q_{hi} = the normalised level of quality attribute $h \in A$ for component i
- $0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$, $t_i \in [t_{min}; t_{max}]$

By combining the objective function and the constraints into a system of inequalities, we obtained a linear optimisation model under constraints for all the characteristics, financial cost and adaptation effort of the software components, defined as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \max \left(\sum_{h \in A} W_h q_{hi} x_i - [\alpha C_i + (1 - \alpha) T_i] x_i \right) \quad \forall i \in \mathbb{N}, x_i \in \{0; 1\} \\ 0 \leq \alpha \leq 1 \\ T_i = \frac{t_{i_rel}}{T_{max}} \text{ et } 0 \leq t_{i_rel} \leq T_{max} \\ C_i = \frac{C_{i_rel}}{C_{max}} \text{ et } 0 \leq C_{i_rel} \leq C_{max} \\ q_{hi} = \frac{q_{hi_rel}}{Q_{max}} \text{ et } 0 \leq q_{hi_rel} \leq C_{max} \\ x = 1 \text{ sélectionné sinon } x = 0 \end{array} \right. \quad (3)$$

Where

- q_{hi} : the normalised level of quality attribute $h \in A$ for component i ;
- W_h : weight assigned to quality attribute $h \in A$;
- x_i : 1 if component i is selected, 0 otherwise;
- C_i : normalised cost of component i ;
- T_i : Normalised maintenance time for component i ;
- α : Adaptation coefficient between 0 and 1

B. Proposed Automated Selection Process

To automate our process, we have built a simulator based on the RecherCompo algorithm. This algorithm aims to select the relevant component from a list of available software components in an ordered list of selected components. It allows us to :

- Express user quality requirements based on three (3) essential points, such as specifying the type of software to be built, choosing a set of software components, and choosing a set of characteristics.
- Verify the consistency of the judgement matrix
- Calculate the weights of the quality characteristics
- Calculate the scores of the software components
- Rank the software components by relevance

Our algorithm is described in previous works [1][3] as follows:

RecherCompo Algorithm

```

1 Input: Pair-wise comparison matrix ( $M_{[i][j]}$ )
2 Output: Ordered list of relevant components from the database (ListComp[ ])
3 Start
4 While (needs and requirements expressed in  $Cd$ ) do
5   For  $i$  from 1 to NumberOfComponents ( $Cd$ ) do
6     For  $j$  from 1 to NumberOfFeatures ( $Ch$ ) do
7       Fill in the comparison matrix ( $M_{[i][j]}$ )
8       Calculate the consistency ratio ( $Rc$ )
9       If ( $Rc \leq 10\%$ )
10        Determine the weight of each characteristic  $W[j]$ 
11     End ifsi
12     Otherwise
13       Resume the comparison matrix ( $M_{[i][j]}$ )
14     End
15   Calculate the score for each component ( $Cd$ )
16   Fill in the list of components (ListeComp[ $i$ ])
17 End
18 Provide the ordered list of relevant components (ComponentList[ ])
19 Wend
20 End
    
```

Fig1 Pseudo code for the RechercCompo algorithm

C. Exact Methods And Limitations

In [1] [3] [14], we developed optimisation models based on constrained integer linear programming to select components meeting user-defined criteria. These models and algorithms enable the identification of a single optimal solution. Sequentially, we can obtain multiple solutions. However, they present limitations such as memory management difficulties and constraints related to the size of the sets used for selection on one hand, and on the other hand, computational time issues for selecting solutions. This is due to the exponential, demanding, and memory-intensive consumption of the solvers used in optimisation tools.

Faced with difficult and NP-complex selection problems that generate several of the aforementioned difficulties, we propose a second approach. This approach consists of selecting software components through a compromise between multiple objectives and through classification based on heuristic artificial intelligence methods.

IV. PROPOSED MODEL

In this article, we propose optimising the selection of software components for different platforms by classification using genetic algorithms. Each platform contains several components with distinct functionalities. The aim is to take into account the type of application to be built and the versions of the components on the one hand, and on the other hand to optimise licence costs, functional coverage and learning times for the selected software components from the libraries.

A. Assumptions

The work we present addresses the selection by group of components from various libraries . We assume that this selection will be carried out under the following conditions :

- The libraries are distinct from one another.
- Each library contains several components, and we must select a set of components from these libraries.
- Each component has several functionalities,
- The components are independent and cover non-overlapping functionalities. This also assumes that there is no overlap between the functionalities of the components

B. Methodology

1) *Platforms* : Our objective is to select an optimal set of software components for a specific type of application to be built.

Therefore, our methodological approach applied in this article consists of identifying software components from platforms, websites and software component marketplaces such as ComponentSource, Zyro, WordPress, Logithèque, etc. We note that ComponentSource is a site for reusable, proprietary components that brings together more than 200 publishers in one place, marketing more than 1,880 software components. It groups together objects such as component types, categories, features and component sale prices. The WordPress site uses reusable software components to build websites efficiently, quickly and securely by facilitating their hosting. It also includes modules, module extensions, site development costs, etc. We will therefore apply the multi-objective optimisation method based on genetic algorithms to classify these components.

2) *The NSGA-II Method* : Several multi-objective methods based on genetic algorithms exist [15] [16]. In [16], the authors

highlighted the different methods of genetic algorithms, mainly elitist methods such as Pareto Archived Evolution Strategy (PAES), Strength Pareto Evolutionary Algorithm (SPEA), Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA) and NSGA-II. It appears that these elitist algorithms favour the selection of the best individuals in the population, i.e. from the set of components to be selected. However, PAES is effective for less complex problems with few objectives. Others are based on clustering, such as SPEA. These algorithms have a low convergence speed and uneven distribution [17] [18]. Given these limitations, we have chosen the NSGA-II method, which remains the most important method due to its balance, reducing complexity on the one hand and facilitating the management of population diversity and data selection through a set of solutions such as the Pareto front on the other. The NSGA-II algorithm is therefore an excellent approach for solving multi-objective

problems, enabling the classification of software components while taking into account the trade-offs associated with several criteria, thereby guaranteeing the preservation of the best results.

C. Proposed Mathematical Model For Multi-Objective Optimisation

In this work, we want to select a set of software components based on quality criteria and from various sources. Each component has quality attributes such as versions, licence cost, functional coverage and learning time. Our objective is to determine a multi-objective optimisation model that takes into account:

- Maximising functional coverage: this refers to all the functionalities provided by the software component. Maximising this involves taking into account the maximum number of functionalities for the system to be developed. We consider the number of expected functionalities that make the component reusable in a system to be built.
- Minimising total licence costs: minimisation involves reducing the overall expenditure on purchasing and managing the licence.
- Minimising overall learning time : this involves reducing the total time required to understand how the selected components work while maintaining the quality of the system.

We will define our various objectives as functions to be minimised or maximised.

1) *Modelling The Cost Of Selected Components* : In this work, we consider that there are several libraries. Each library contains selectable components. Therefore, we need to model the total cost total CT_{otal} of N components selected from various P libraries. Let f_{Cost} be a function defined from the Cartesian set of n libraries to the set of real numbers. The cost, which is a score, will be stored in a list.

$$f_{Cost}: \begin{matrix} \mathbb{R}^n & \rightarrow & \mathbb{R} \\ (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_i, \dots, X_N) & \rightarrow & CT_{otal} \end{matrix}$$

The function f_{Cost} becomes

$$f_{Cost}: \begin{matrix} B_1 \times B_2 \times \dots \times B_i \times \dots \times B_N & \rightarrow & \mathbb{R} \\ (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_i, \dots, X_N) & \rightarrow & CT_{otal} \end{matrix} \tag{4}$$

where

B_i : is the library with index $i, i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$

N : Total number of libraries

X_i : n - tuples of P components

$X_i \in \{Comp_i^1, Comp_i^2, \dots, Comp_i^j, \dots, Comp_i^P\}$

$Comp_i^j$: component j of labrary i

$j \in \{1, 2, \dots, M_i\}$

M_i : Number of components of B_i

CT_{otal} : total cost of licenses for the components used

Considering that C_{ij} denotes the licence cost of component j in library i , then the total cost of the selected components is :

$$CT_{otal} = \sum_i^N \sum_j^{M_i} C_{ij} \tag{5}$$

This amounts to calculating the total cost for a single library i and then aggregating across all libraries.

These scores will be ranked in a list and we retrieve the $\min(f_{cost})$ of these calculated totals

2) *Modelling the total learning time associated with the selected components* : Our second objective is to minimise the

learning time for the components used to build the application. As in paragraph 2.1, we model the total time TT_{otal} for N components selected from P libraries. Let f_{Times} be a function defined from the Cartesian set of n libraries to the set of real numbers.

$$f_{Times}: \begin{matrix} \mathbb{R}^n & \rightarrow & \mathbb{R} \\ (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_i, \dots, X_N) & \rightarrow & TT_{total} \end{matrix}$$

The function f_{Times} becomes

$$f_{Times}: \begin{matrix} B_1 \times B_2 \times \dots \times B_i \times \dots \times B_N & \rightarrow & \mathbb{R} \\ (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_i, \dots, X_N) & \rightarrow & TT_{total} \end{matrix} \tag{6}$$

where

B_i : is the library with index $i, i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$

N : Total number of libraries

X_i : n – tuples of P components

$X_i \in \{Comp_i^1, Comp_i^2, \dots, Comp_i^j, \dots, Comp_i^P\}$

$Comp_i^j$: component j of library i

$j \in \{1, 2, \dots, M_i\}$

M_i : Number of components of B_i

TT_{total} : total learning time for the components used

Considering that t_{ij} denotes the learning time associated with component j in library i , then the total learning time of the components selected and used to build our software application is:

These scores will be sorted into a list and we retrieve the $\min(f_{Times})$ of these calculated totals.

$$TT_{total} = \sum_i^N \sum_j^{M_i} t_{ij} \tag{7}$$

3) *Modelling functional coverage of selected components*: We want to count the number of features per component and per library.

Assumption: We assume that the components are independent and that their functionalities are different from one another. This also assumes that there is no overlap between the functionalities of the components.

Let f_{Nfct} , a function defined from the Cartesian set of n libraries to the set of real numbers

$$f_{Nfct}: \begin{matrix} B_1 \times B_2 \times \dots \times B_i \times \dots \times B_N & \rightarrow & \mathbb{R} \\ (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_i, \dots, X_N) & \rightarrow & N_b T_{total} \end{matrix}$$

where

B_i : is the library with index $i, i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$

N : Total number of libraries

X_i : n – tuples of P components

$X_i \in \{Comp_i^1, Comp_i^2, \dots, Comp_i^j, \dots, Comp_i^P\}$

$Comp_i^j$: component j of library i

$j \in \{1, 2, \dots, M_i\}$

M_i : Number of components of B_i

$N_b T_{total}$: total number of covered features

(8)

Considering that $N_b f_{ij}$ denotes the number of features covered by component j in library i , without overlap, then the total number of features of the components selected and used to build our software application is:

$$N_b T_{total} = \sum_i^N \sum_j^{M_i} N_b f_{ij} \tag{9}$$

These scores will be ranked in a list and we retrieve the $\max(f_{Nfct})$ of these calculated totals.

4) *Summary*: In this article, our approach is to optimise the selection of software components in libraries using three

objectives : minimising licence costs, minimising learning time, and maximising the functional coverage of the selected library components. This gives us the following model :

$$\begin{cases} \text{minimize}(f_{cost}(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_i, \dots, X_N)) = CT_{total} \\ \text{minimize}(f_{Temps}(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_i, \dots, X_N)) = TT_{total} \\ \text{maximize}(f_{Nfct}(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_i, \dots, X_N)) = N_bT_{total} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Considering the constraints, the system becomes:

$$\begin{cases} \min \left(\sum_i^N \sum_j^{M_i} C_{ij} \right) x_{ij} = CT_{total} \\ \min \left(\sum_i^N \sum_j^{M_i} t_{ij} \right) x_{ij} = TT_{total} \\ \max \left(\sum_i^N \sum_j^{M_i} N_b f_{ij} \right) x_{ij} = N_bT_{total} \\ C_{ij} \geq 0 \text{ et } t_{ij} \geq 0 \text{ et } N_b f_{ij} \geq 0 \\ F_i \subseteq F \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where

i : index of the library, $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$

j : index of component, $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, M_i\}$

M_i : number of components of B_i

N : total number of libraries

C_{ij} : cost of the license for component j from library i

t_{ij} : learning time associated with component j in library i

$N_b f_{ij}$: number of features covered by component j in library i

x_{ij} : component j selected from library i

CT_{total} : total cost of licenses for the components used

N_bT_{total} : total number of covered features

TT_{total} : total learning time for the components used

F : set of all component features

F_i : features covered by component j from library i

5) *Decision variables* : The decision variables of a problem are the variables that will impact the solution to the problem

[16]. They represent the useful quantities on which decisions will be made. We have defined the following four decision variables :

- x_{ij} : Boolean variable for selecting component j from library i

$$\begin{cases} x_{ij} = 1 \text{ for selected component} \\ x_{ij} = 0 \text{ else} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

- C_{ij} : real variable denoting the cost of component j of library i
- t_{ij} : v real variable denoting the learning time associated with component j of library i .
- $N_b f_{ij}$: real variable denoting the functional coverage of component j of library i .

D. Proposed Selection Algorithm

Based on our multi-objective optimisation model developed above, we want to obtain a set of non-dominated solutions. This is a set of solutions that represent the best possible compromises between conflicting objectives such as minimising licence costs, maximising functional coverage and minimising the learning time for the selected software. In this subset of solutions, no solution dominates another. For example, when selecting software components for building a banking system, we find that high-end, premium components are very expensive but cover a maximum number of features. Conversely, economical components are inexpensive but severely limited in functionality. Thus, the best compromises in the graphical representation

form a boundary known as the Pareto front. The authors [19] [20] proposed in their work the non-dominated sorting in NSGA-II for solving complex multi-objective optimisation problems.

1) *Functioning Of The Algorithm* : We improve the optimisation of software component selection developed in [1] [3]

using the NSGA-II algorithm. It consists of combining multi-objective optimisation and automatic component classification for a selection that is better suited to the types of software applications to be built. The application of the NSGA-II multi-objective optimisation algorithm involves five (5) different steps.

- *Step 1: creation of the initial population (P0)*

This step consists of defining a process that generates a set of software components from different libraries. This is the first generation of our algorithm. The characteristics of the components take into account both defined objectives such as licence cost, functional coverage and learning time, and the type of software to be developed, including search engines, databases, banking transactions, user interfaces, etc. Thus, the solutions are represented by binary vector encoding.

Our selections are based on a set of libraries, each containing components. We have :

- $\cup B_i, i \in \{1,2, \dots, n\}$, a set of libraries where B_i designates the library i
- $X_i = \{Comp_i^1, Comp_i^1, \dots, Comp_i^j, \dots, Comp_i^N\}$

Where

X_i is the set of N software components available in the library B_i

$Comp_i^j$: represents the component j of the library i

- A set of selected software components is considered a solution and represented by a binary vector of k bits depending on the K constraints to be satisfied and related to the type of system to be built. In this case, the bit i can take the value 0 or 1. We have :

$$\begin{cases} i = 1 & \text{if selected component} \\ i = 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

Let us consider that we have components available in three libraries. A selection is a solution or a chromosome represented by a 7-bit binary vector where each gene corresponds to a component selected or not selected in Fig 2. We can obtain:

Fig. 2 Set of selected components representing a solution

For this solution, the selected components are $\{Comp_1^1, Comp_2^1, Comp_3^1, Comp_3^2\}$. These are *component1* of B_1 , *component1* of B_2 and *components2* and *3* of B_3 where B_i is the library i

The population P_0 is the set of all possible selections.

$$P_0 = \cup S_{i \in \{1, \dots, P\}}$$

where S_i is the chromosome i

- *Step 2: evaluation of each selection*

This step consists of taking into account the multi-objective function on the one hand and the classification of solutions into non-dominance fronts on the other. Our multi-objective function is defined by equation (12) in Chapter 3. The aim is to minimise the total cost of licences, minimise the total learning time and maximise the total functional coverage of the selected software components from the different libraries for a given solution. So, for each chromosome, we calculate the total values according to the defined objectives and then evaluate all the solution options using scores. This evaluation is based on the organisation of the population into several levels of quality using the concept of dominance. In [21], the authors highlighted the concept of dominance and then presented the objectives of Pareto front ranking in the following three key points :

- Preserving diversity,
- Promoting convergence towards the optimal Pareto frontier,
- Guiding selection towards the best solutions.

At this stage, we mainly determine the scores of the chromosomes. Considering the data table 1 below from three libraries

$$B = \cup B_i, i \in \{1,2,3\}$$

TABLE I
SOFTWARE COMPONENTS OF DIFFERENT LIBRARIES AND THEIR CHARACTERISTICS

Components	Costs (\$)	Learning time (h)	Features	Type of Components
$Comp_1^1$	1200	15	9	Framework
$Comp_1^2$	800	25	7	Library
$Comp_1^3$	500	40	5	Plugin
$Comp_2^1$	150	10	10	Platform
$Comp_2^2$	300	35	4	Tool
$Comp_2^3$	2000	5	12	Continued
$Comp_3^1$	600	20	6	Middleware
$Comp_3^2$	900	30	8	Library
$Comp_3^3$	400	45	3	Plugin
$Comp_4^3$	1100	12	11	Framework

Considering two random combinations of chromosomes 1 and 2 designating solutions with genes represented on binary vectors of length $l = 10$ bits. We obtain:

Chromosome 1 : [0,1,1,0,1,0,1,0,1,0]

Chromosome 2 : [1,0,0,1,0,1,0,1,0,1]

For chromosome1, the selected components are: $Comp_1^2, Comp_1^3, Comp_2^2, Comp_3^1, Comp_3^3$. we have:

$$\begin{cases} CT_{total} = 800 + 500 + 300 + 600 + 400 = 2600 \text{ en } \$ \\ TT_{total} = 25 + 40 + 35 + 20 + 45 = 165 \text{ en heures} \\ N_b T_{total} = 7 + 5 + 4 + 6 + 3 = 25 \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

For chromosome2, the selected components are: $Comp_1^1, Comp_2^1, Comp_3^2, Comp_3^3, Comp_4^3$

We obtain

$$\begin{cases} CT_{total} = 1200 + 1500 + 2000 + 900 + 1100 = 6700 \text{ en } \$ \\ TT_{total} = 15 + 10 + 5 + 30 + 12 = 72 \text{ en heures} \\ N_b T_{total} = 9 + 10 + 12 + 8 + 11 = 50 \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

In the same way, we evaluate the N possible solutions representing all component selections.

- *Step 3: non-dominated solution and Pareto front*

The Pareto front allows us to move from the optimisation algorithm phase to the decision phase. The NSGA-II algorithm aims to reveal all the optimal solution options. It is then up to the decision-maker to make the choice according to strategic preferences and contextual constraints [22]. We therefore move from optimisation to informed decision-making.

B_i Considering a library space comprising N software components, we obtain 2^N combinations representing the possible solutions. For 10 components to be selected, we then obtain $2^{10} = 1024$ possible choices. For each pair of solutions, we will study the dominance of one component over the other.

But what is the notion of dominance? The notion of dominance is defined as follows:

Considering S_i and S_j with $i \neq j$ and $i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ two solutions of n ($n = 7$)-bits chromosomes from the universe of all possible solutions, approximately 1024 solutions. We say that S_i dominates S_j if:

$$\begin{aligned} & - CT_{total}(S_i) \leq CT_{total}(S_j) \\ & - TT_{total}(S_i) \leq TT_{total}(S_j) \\ & - N_b T_{total}(S_i) \geq N_b T_{total}(S_j) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Equation (15) means that the solution S_i is at least as good as S_j for all defined objectives, or that S_i is significantly better than S_j for at least one objective. From the table 1, considérons S_1, S_2 et S_3 of 7-bit chromosome solutions among all possible solutions, we have:

$S_1 = \{Comp_2^3, Comp_3^1\}$; $S_2 = \{Comp_1^3, Comp_1^3, Comp_3^4\}$; $S_3 = \{Comp_1^1, Comp_2^1, Comp_4^3\}$

To verify whether our three objectives have been achieved, we check the dominance of S_1 over S_2 .

$$\text{We obtain : } \begin{cases} S_1. CT_{total}(900) < S_2. CT_{total}(2200) \\ S_1. TT_{total}(55) < S_2. TT_{total}(72) \\ S_1. N_b T_{total}(10) < S_2. N_b T_{total}(220) \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

The cost and learning time of S_1 are minimised compared to those of S_2 . However, the number of features of S_1 is not maximised compared to that of S_2 . Therefore, S_1 does not dominate S_2 . We would say that between S_1 and S_2 , no solution dominates the other and we are faced with conflicting objectives. The same applies to S_2 and S_3 , and S_1 , and S_3 .

$$\begin{cases} S_2 \cdot CT_{total}(2200) < S_3 \cdot CT_{total}(3800) \\ S_2 \cdot TT_{total}(72) > S_3 \cdot TT_{total}(37) \\ S_2 \cdot NbT_{total}(22) < S_3 \cdot CT_{total}(30) \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{cases} S_1 \cdot CT_{total}(900) < S_3 \cdot CT_{total}(3800) \\ S_1 \cdot TT_{total}(55) > S_3 \cdot TT_{total}(37) \\ S_1 \cdot NbT_{total}(10) < S_3 \cdot CT_{total}(30) \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

For system (17), the time S_2 is not minimised compared to that of S_3 on the one hand, and on the other hand, the number of features is not maximised either. We note that the objectives are conflicting. Therefore, there is no dominance of one over the other for the solutions S_1 , S_2 , and S_3 . Our objective is to find solutions that represent compromises between the various conflicting objectives. We consider the set of non-dominated solutions, which is a set representing the Pareto front.

What is the Pareto Front and what are its objectives? The Pareto front represents the set of non-dominated solutions in a multi-objective optimization problem with conflicting goals [23]. This front provides a comprehensive analysis of the solutions offering the best compromise between different criteria. It thus represents the best trade-offs found by the NSGA-II algorithm after convergence. Its value lies in the clear and quantitative graphical visualization of the trade-offs between solutions with conflicting objectives, such as minimizing license cost and learning time while maximizing the number of features. Solving our problem involves evaluating all component combinations that are subsets or parts of the set of libraries B , $B = \cup B_i$, ou B_i is library i with $i \in \{1,2,3\}$.

Our implemented NSGA-II algorithm explores all combinatorial subsets or solutions and efficiently determines optimal solutions near the Pareto front for the three objectives. This performance is governed by three key parameters: the chosen population size, the number of generations (which serves as the stopping criterion), and the distribution of objectives in the solution space. For our case, if we consider the library set $B = \cup B_i$, $i \in \{1,2,3\}$ and containing 10 components. Therefore, our initial population is $P_0 = N = 2^{10} = 1024$ combinations of software components, which includes both the empty set (or minimal solution) and the set containing all components (or maximal solution). The literature indicates that when the population size is too small, it risks premature convergence. Conversely, an excessively large population size leads to prolonged and unnecessary computation. The recommended population size is between 50 and 100 to choose $N \leq 10$ components to be selected. Given the constraints mentioned above, we consider the following NSGA-II algorithm parameters for the subsequent work:

Population size $P = 50$ individuals
Generations = 100
Crossover rate = 0.9
Mutation rate = 0.3

The solutions on front F_1 concern components or component combinations from the second-best category. These include components with less favorable trade-offs than those in F_0 , but which are still relevant. Therefore, front F_1 represents the set of solutions that are dominated only by solutions from front F_0 . These solutions are positioned just below those of F_0 . In the same manner, we reach front F_n . This final front contains the solutions of the lowest quality in terms of domination.

V. DISCUSSIONS

Our problem is to select a subset from the universe of software components, choosing among P available

components. This selection must represent a compromise between the three (3) objectives defined by our objective function. The Pareto front serves to display a set of optimal, non-dominated solutions. We are not seeking a single, so-called "best" solution. Therefore, each solution on the Pareto front is a point of equilibrium between license cost, time dedicated to learning, and the number of features covered by the component. Consequently, all solutions must be optimal in their trade-offs. Thus, decision-makers will incorporate the notions of preference and constraints to make their choice.

Indeed, we observe that when solutions have more features, they entail a higher license cost.

Furthermore,

it is possible to note that when learning time is low, the number of features is reduced and the license cost is lower. Our final observation is that when license cost is reduced, the number of features is also reduced, and learning time is increased. Within these contexts, for a small company or startup with a stronger budgetary constraint, decision-makers will have the option to choose solutions with lower license costs, such as tools and plugins. Additionally, they can choose from the set of open-source software components where the license cost is null. However, large companies without budgetary constraints might opt for higher performance software components, selecting combinations with a significant number of features. These companies can utilize premium versions in their projects. Ultimately, the ideal solution depends on user priorities related to budgetary constraints, project implementation timelines, and software component performance. Thus, our work serves as a common interface between the financial department for the budget, the technical team for timeline management, and the management of the software component to be selected.

VI. CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVE

The construction of a high-quality modular application depends on the selection of optimal software component solutions from various libraries. In this article, we have proposed a multi-objective optimization model based on the NSGA-II algorithm to facilitate the selection of software components from three (3) libraries. Our results model a multi-objective optimization framework that accounts for optimal solutions representing trade-offs between conflicting objectives such as licensing cost, learning time, and functional coverage of the software components. These solutions can be represented on a Pareto front. Thus, project decision-makers and developers can make their choices based on corporate budget constraints, decision-maker preferences, project deadlines, and target performance levels. In this context, we show that software component selection is therefore based on organizational constraints. Hence, our work transforms a combinatorial optimization problem into a strategic decision-making process for solving complex problems for developers and companies. In future work, we will evaluate our models and then analyze software component selection through classification, taking into account the type of application to be developed and incorporating artificial intelligence algorithms.

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